

SOCIAL HOUSING POLICIES — POSSIBILITIES FOR WOMEN WHO HAVE SURVIVED VIOLENCE, AND HOW THEY CAN REALIZE THEIR RIGHTS

Vedrana Lacmanović
Aleksandra Nestorov

*autonomous
women's
center
belgrade*

 Austrian
Development
Agency

SOCIAL HOUSING POLICIES — POSSIBILITIES FOR WOMEN WHO HAVE SURVIVED VIOLENCE, AND HOW THEY CAN REALIZE THEIR RIGHTS

Publisher:	Autonomous Women's Centre
Author:	MA Vedrana Lacmanović and Aleksandra Nestorov
Expert consultation:	Ph.D. Tanja Ignjatović
Translation:	Nina Đurđević Filipović
Design:	Rastko Toholj
Published:	2021
ISBN:	978-86-87505-40-7

 Austrian
Development
Agency

Project *Institutionalizing quality rehabilitation and integration services for violence survivors* is funded by the Austrian Development Agency (ADA) with funds of Austrian Development Cooperation.

Contents

1. Social housing policies — possibilities for women who have survived violence, and how they can realize their rights	5
1.1. Introduction	5
1.2. Analysis focus and goals	7
1.3. Methodology, challenges and limitations	7
2. Housing needs and housing insecurity of women (surviving violence)	9
3. Serbia’s social housing legal framework (in relation to women who have survived violence as a distinct target group)	12
4. Legal framework of social housing policy in the city of belgrade (for the target group of women who have survived violence)	16
4.1. Exercising social housing policy rights in practice on the territory of the City of Belgrade	21
5. Social housing policy models (pertaining to women who have survived violence) — examples from the European Union	24
5.1. Half-way house for women victims of violence, Skoplje, North Macedonia	26
5.2. Comprehensive model of social housing accessible to all: Vienna, Austria	27
6. Conclusion	29
7. Literature	32
8. Documents	34

I. SOCIAL HOUSING POLICIES — POSSIBILITIES FOR WOMEN WHO HAVE SURVIVED VIOLENCE, AND HOW THEY CAN REALIZE THEIR RIGHTS

1.1. Introduction

Social housing is a phrase used to describe non-profit apartment renting, while the target groups it is made available to are people in risk of homelessness or people without adequate housing (they may live in housing that does not fulfil criteria regarding basic necessities, electrical installations and plumbing, construction safety and security, protection from outside elements, and basic hygienic necessities). Instead of the phrase social housing the current Housing and Building Maintenance Act uses the term housing support which has been defined as “every means of support provided to people who, because of social, financial or other reasons, cannot independently afford to pay market prices and solve their and their family’s housing needs”. **Social housing is just one of the measures/strategies of social housing policies** that aim to eradicate social exclusion and poverty. **Aside from providing apartments for rent, social housing policies may include measures such as purchasing apartments for (potentially) homeless people, tax deductions in relation to purchasing of property and yearly property tax, affordable property bank loans, financial assistance for renovating inadequate apartments, a deduction or complete dismissal of all monthly bills for the apartment — subventions and such.** The aim of this policy is to provide everyone in society with adequately furnished apartments, of adequate size and quality, in surroundings with adequate infrastructure and all at an affordable price (Economic Commission for Europe Geneva, 2006, pg. 9). These apartments are usually state owned, but they may also be jointly owned by the state and nonprofit organizations.

During the last thirty years we could observe an obvious lack of comprehensive housing policies in Serbia, even though the need for housing has significantly increased. The old socialist era housing stock has been almost completely privatized since the ninety nineties, while public financing of housing has been eliminated because the new purely capitalist approach dictates the housing is something that should only be regulated by the market. After mass privatization the housing fund was almost completely depleted, but privatization did not secure financial resources to develop a new housing fund. Hence, housing provision for those most in need has been completely disabled. Unlike Serbia where social housing accounts for 0.78% of overall housing (National Housing Strategy draft 2020-2030, 2020), certain European countries (which have a far greater overall living standard) boast a 15% to 35%¹ social housing rate (OECD Affordable Housing Database; OECD —

1 Data base of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development shows that the following countries have the largest percentage of social housing: The Netherlands (35%), Denmark (20%), Austria (20%), Great Britain (18%), and France (15%).

Social Policy Division — Directorate of Employment, Labor and Social Affairs, 2020, pg. 2) — a fact we should keep in mind in relation to Serbia's EU integration plans.

The first social housing programs (in the modern interpretation of the phrase) in Serbia can be traced to the Refugee Housing and Integration Program deployed from 2004 to 2008², even though this program faced major hurdles due to the total lack of a strategic framework in this sector. From that time till now there have been occasional and sporadic programs aimed at improving social housing, and those were mostly financed by donations from foreign governments or international organizations. When it comes to an institutional framework it must be noted that so far social housing programs were conducted by various state institutions, local self-governments, and international organizations (PALGO Center, 2010: 49). Previous analyses show that housing policy was spurred on by short-term political goals — an approach that, long-term, resulted in further demolition of institutions that were painstakingly built for decades. We can also notice that new systemic solutions have been proposed, but they weren't part of a consistent long-term policy. Rather they were only partial initiatives made by some (relevant) institutions, which in turn resulted in development of several similar instruments, overlap of programs intended for the same target groups but under different terms, and an obvious lack of coordination among sectors and different levels of authority (PALGO Center, 2010: 19). Considering all of these facts we can deduce that social housing policies in Serbia have been ad hoc and erratic, rather than systematic, coordinated and long-term, as it should be in order to achieve social cohesion, sustainable development and overall social improvement.

Women victims of violence have remained absolutely invisible as a target group of social housing measures, that is, of social housing policy in the Republic of Serbia. Namely, existing programs were aimed at: internally displaced people and refugees; young University of Belgrade employees, as well as those at Novi Sad and Nis universities; residents of certain local self-government units; health sector employees; those employed in the military; financially insecure households with low income; those employed in institutions which are financed by the state budget, etc. (PALGO Center, 2010: 33-40). Even though the target groups of social housing policies have been diverse, and sourced from a wide area of people — everyone who is in need of support and help in realizing their right to housing, that is, those who do not have the means to afford market prices of adequate housing (their own or rented), under the terms and conditions as set out by law (PALGO Center, 2010: 13), the Republic of Serbia has none the less not developed any programs aimed at women surviving violence as a distinct target group. Going forward, such programs should be developed, seeing as target groups should be defined in accordance to the state's and communities' means, as well as in accordance to specific circumstances and problems that must be regulated by laws and rules (PALGO Center, 2010: 13), and in consideration to the fact that violence against women is a widespread social problem.

When we analyze housing in Serbia in its wider context, we can notice some characteristics that stand out: a large aging population, increased numbers of smaller households, erratic urbanization,

2 This program was made possible with donations from the Italian government in cooperation with UN-HABITAT, units of local self-government and relevant state bodies.

illegal construction, development of informal housing areas, and migrations out of rural areas. From the perspective of social cohesion, current housing opportunities prove to be worrisome considering “that 7.3% of the Serbian populace lives in absolute poverty, half a million people aren’t able to satisfy basic needs, and that the percentage of people in risk of poverty or social exclusion is highest among all European nations at 38.7%, the risk of poverty rate is 25.5%, while only 3.7% of the population receives social assistance (the European Commission’s report on the Republic of Serbia 2018-2019; Ignjatovic, 2020, pg. 6)”. Despite all of this, housing poverty has not been adequately addressed and systemically included into social welfare policy, that is, aside from taking into consideration existential needs the criteria for determining the level of risk of poverty does not really consider housing needs. Keeping all of this in mind it is evident that the state must reassert itself and become more active in the housing sector, especially so in relation to creating measures and implementing social housing policies. Therefore, it is important to note that social housing must be included in social inclusion and cohesions policies, but also in policies pertaining to regional and local development, as these are connected to sustainable development overall (PALGO Center, 2010: 10).

1.2. Analysis focus and goals

The focus of this analysis was to map out housing needs and housing insecurity among women who have survived violence (and who used the services of the Autonomous Women’s Center from 2015 to 2020), to review and analyze the statewide legal framework of social housing policies, as well as in Belgrade specifically, and how these measures have been put into practice in relation to women who have survived violence. The goal was to open up a public discussion based on data provided by this analysis and initiate legal and practical measures which would address the needs of women surviving violence.

1.3. Methodology, challenges and limitations

Research for the analysis encompassed:

- Analysis of housing needs and degree of vulnerability of women who has survived violence and who used the services of the Autonomous Women’s Center from 2015 to 2020; the analysis was conducted based on the organization’s records.
- Collecting documents, reviewing and presenting the existing positive legal framework of social housing policies in Serbia
- Collecting documents, reviewing and presenting the existing positive legal framework of social housing policies in the city of Belgrade
- Collecting information, reviewing and presenting how social housing rights have been realized on the territory of Belgrade for women who have survived violence as a specific target group (from 2002 to 2020)
- Analyzing and presenting European social housing policy models, and how they work out in practice (in relation to women who are surviving violence)

Limitations in mapping the target of the said research were mostly caused by the incongruity of legal documents; a long time period which was to be covered by the analysis of public policy in this area (starting from the time the criminal act of domestic violence was made law till today, that is, from 2002 to 2020), and the fact that the practice of designing, creating and accomplishing the measures of said policy was very deficient and modest.

2. HOUSING NEEDS AND HOUSING INSECURITY OF WOMEN (SURVIVING VIOLENCE)

Women in Serbia are property owners in only 39.2% of cases (The Commissioner for the Protection of Equality, 2015). Women make up 17.3% of owners or co-owners of agricultural land (the Republic Statistics Bureau, 2014).

Out of the total of 25 million registered immovable assets in rural and urban Serbia, women own or co-own only 6.43 million. They own 13.95% of real-estate, and co-own 12%. While 25% of men in Serbia own an apartment, only 14.6% of women do so (NALED, 2020). In comparison to men, women are far less often owners of property, which in itself represents major financial capital — apartments, office space, land, etc. (National Gender Equality Strategy 2016-2020).

Aside from the issue of inequality in relation to securing goods and services (in the aforementioned case, real-estate), women also face the fact that they earn less money than men (the Republic Statistics Bureau, 2017). Women are in a far more disadvantageous position than men in Serbia in both these regards — a reality that reflects on their status within the family and partner relations. Due to inability to secure alternative living arrangements and better lives for themselves and their children, women who lack financial means are at greater risk of: becoming victims of violence, hiding the violence they've survived, delaying reporting the abuser to authorities.

The Autonomous Women's Center's report "Poverty Risks Faced by Women Who Have Experienced Violence", published in 2012, had shown that having access to housing directly influences a woman's decision to leave a violent relationship and become independent. Women who are surviving violence in most cases either don't have access to housing of their own, or they have access to temporary housing. Aside from lack of housing, or having inadequate furnishing and bad hygienic conditions, these women are also exposed to constant uncertainty and fear. They are forced to move apartments frequently due to lack of resources, but also because of discrimination from landlords against divorced women and single mothers; or because they have to cancel the lease of an apartment where they have suffered violence. They are unable to use legally available deductions for paying monthly bills seeing as they live in rented apartments — and most of them live in housing that is not their property. Unemployed women have difficulty acquiring the funds to pay rent and monthly bills, especially so if they are refugees or internally displaced women, or Roma women (Ignjatovic, Pesic, 2012, pg. 12). The Autonomous Women's Center's most recent data shows that out of 721 women who have experienced violence in a partner context, most were from Belgrade and have had individual consultations at AWC, while every third woman (38.5%) expressed wanting to solve her housing issues on a more permanent level. None of them were living in social housing intended for vulnerable social groups, nor had access to financial support for paying rent and monthly bills, or other means of housing support (Ignjatovic, 2021).

A report compiled by the Roma Center for Women and Children “Daje” from Belgrade — “Gender Based Violence against Roma Women, and Access to Support Services” states that most Roma women live in homes that are owned by their partners and/or their partner’s family, as well as that 78.7% of them are unemployed. Women who were interviewed for this report while living in safe houses noted that they will face difficulties upon leaving said safe houses because they have nowhere to go — a frequent reason as to why women go back to their abusers. In that sense, authors of the report suggest that it necessary to financially empower Roma women — halfway houses are cited as one possible option in this regard (Marinkovic, Durickovic, and Bicic, 2019).

Data compiled by the Autonomous Women’s Center shows that out of the 721 women who required written legal assistance in the last five years, only 196 (27.18%) reported that they that they owned or co-owned the house/apartment they lived in. Out of those women, only 77 (10.68%) live in a house/apartment that is their sole property. The data we gathered in this regard will be expanded on further in the text.

Analyzing the housing status of 721 women who used the Autonomous Women’s Center’s written legal service aid (from 2016 to 2020), we concluded that at the time 696 were living in Belgrade, while 25 were living in other towns and municipalities in Serbia.

The most frequent reason for turning to the Autonomous Women’s Center was domestic violence (610 cases), while 109 women came to seek help regarding financial violence in the form of the abusers’ disregard for alimony, and other legal issues pertaining to family life: loss of parental rights, establishing paternity, divorce, putting children into care and regulating child visitation. Two women sought help to get access to financial aid.

Out of the 721 women who sought help from the Autonomous Women’s Center more than half (368) were their children’s sole providers and direct caretakers at the time. Research has shown that financial and housing security are the most prevalent and well documented problems faced by single parent households — mothers making up the majority of such cases. A specific aspect of material deprivation is housing deprivation, which frequently results in moving locations and changing types of housing after divorce, most often to worse housing in a worse neighborhood (Tomanovic, Ljubicic, Stanojevic, 2014).

Out of the 721 women who turned to AWC’s legal aid service for help, **165 noted that they were living in temporary accommodations.** Out of those 122 were renting an apartment, 7 were at safe houses for victims of domestic violence and maternity home, 2 women were temporarily living with their female neighbor or in an apartment they have temporarily been granted access to. There is no data pertaining to the other 44 women and what type of temporary shelter they were living in.

Out of the 721 women, a total of **216** who used AWC’s legal aid service noted that they were living with their parents or friends, out of which 117 lived with their parents. 8 women noted they were living with their brother/sister/daughter/family member, 7 with friends, while 84 women did not explain what type of shelter in this regard they were living in.

196 women noted they had complete or partially ownership of a house or an apartment, out of the 721 women who used AWC's legal aid service. 77 of them noted they were living in their own apartment or house, while 50 women noted they were living in a property they co-owned, and 69 women did not explain what type of ownership status they had.

70 women who turned to AWC's legal aid services for help noted that they **were living in their partner's or their partner's family's property**. 28 women were living in their partner's apartment or house, 18 were living in his family's property, while 24 women did not explain what type of housing they were living in.

For a total of 74 out of the 721 women there is no data pertaining to ownership of real-estate they were living in at the time.

It's important to note that aside from being at risk of becoming victims of violence, women with inadequate financial means / who lack of housing also face a risk of becoming homeless in case they leave the abusive partner or family member.

According to census data from 2011, Serbia had 18 287 homeless people. **The largest group is comprised of women over the age of 65** (National Housing Strategy draft 2020-2030). Violence suffered at the hands of an intimate male partner is cited as the strongest factor contributing to female homelessness. Research conducted in many countries shows that the percentage of female domestic violence victims among the homeless varies around 40% in Great Britain and Ireland, to 50% in Portugal and Hungary. While Spain and Sweden had an extremely high number of female homelessness people who experienced violence from their male partner at 100% and 93% respectively (European Federation of National Organizations Working with the Homeless).

It's commendable that the Housing and Building Maintenance Act, in Article 89, recognizes victims of domestic violence as one of the eight distinct target groups for which housing support measures are intended. However, aside from the possibility of accessing safe houses for domestic violence — a necessary but temporary solution — there are still no permanent and sustainable measures aimed at providing housing to victims of domestic violence on a statewide level (National Housing Strategy draft, 2020-2030). *The GREVIO expert report on the basic assessment of legal and other measures for implementing the Council of Europe's Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (2020)*, notes that women victims of violence are offered social housing options and specific employment services, that the National Social Housing Strategy 2021-2022 foresees special measures for victims of domestic violence who need housing assistance, while the National Employment Service's Program for Employment contains provisions pertaining to subventions for employers who open new work positions. However, in conclusion, the report notes that the impact of these new programs is expected to be minor due to the fact that only a small number of municipalities offer social housing to victims of domestic violence.

3. SERBIA'S SOCIAL HOUSING LEGAL FRAMEWORK (IN RELATION TO WOMEN WHO HAVE SURVIVED VIOLENCE AS A DISTINCT TARGET GROUP)

The Constitution of The Republic of Serbia does not explicitly regulate the right to housing, but provisions pertaining to social security (Article 69) and fulfilment of basic human needs based on social justice principles, humanism and human dignity, may be interpreted as providing ground for the right to housing. Especially so considering that housing is a basic human need and that those who need social security benefits are at greater risk of not being able to fulfil this need. The Constitution also directs the state to “regulate and secure a social security system, sustainable development, basic aims and developmental directions of regional and social development, policies and measures for directing and motivating development, property and obligational relations, and other relations which are of interest to the Republic of Serbia” (Article 97, point 9).

Even though the Constitution of the Republic of Serbia does not explicitly mention the right to housing as a human right, it has become an integral part of domestic legislation also through the adoption and ratification of international legal documents such as:

Universal Declaration of Human Rights — which proclaims that everybody has a right to a standard of living which secures health and wellbeing for a person and his/her family, including housing (Article 25). As every other signatory of the declaration Serbia is obligated to respect this stipulation.

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights — which obliges signatories to respect every individual's right to a good standard of living for them and their family, including the right to housing. Signatories are also obliged to adopt measures that secure said rights can be exercised, and emphasize the importance of international cooperation (Article 11, point 1).

The European Social Charter (revised) obliges signatories in Article 31 to adopt measures aimed at securing adequate housing, prevent or decrease homelessness, as well as ensure that housing prices are affordable to those who do not have adequate financial means.

The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence directs signatories to take the necessary legal, and other, measures to ensure that victims have access to services aiding their recovery from violence, with housing being one of the required needs (Article 20, point 1).

The Geneva UN Charter on Sustainable Housing is a newer international legal document regulating this issue, and even though it isn't legally binding, it provides direction for developing national housing policies in accordance to current global trends, and fosters cooperation among

states in regards to housing. The Charter aims at ensuring provision of appropriate, adequate, accessible, and healthy housing for all, while special attention is paid to creating housing policies in accordance with the principles of environmental protection and social inclusion. Chapter 1, point 5, emphasizes the importance of providing housing to the poor, disadvantaged and vulnerable (domestic violence victims among others).

The Public Property Act directly regulates public property rights and other property rights in the Republic of Serbia, its autonomous provinces and self-government units; decision-making, usage, and management of public property; scope of people who may use public property; acquisition, handling and management of private property items; record keeping, jurisdiction and oversight. In relation to social housing, the most important article is the one defining public property residential buildings as “residential buildings, apartments, garages and office space in residential buildings, which have been acquired by the Republic of Serbia, its autonomous provinces or self-government units by means of construction, purchase or other types of means” (Article 54, point 1). Additionally, it stipulates that residential buildings and apartments intended for social housing also fall under this category, but that their use is legally regulated by a different law (Article 54, point 1).

Housing and Building Maintenance Act is the law which regulates social housing in more detail, and in several articles it acknowledges victims of violence as a distinct target group:

- It obligates the state and other institutions, as well as other actors involved in eviction and moving procedures to carry out the law in accordance to the principle of especially protecting vulnerable groups, with domestic violence victims being one of them (Article 80, para 4);
- The Act explicitly lists domestic violence victims who don’t have an apartment or adequate housing, who don’t have adequate means to independently solve their need for housing, as beneficiaries of social housing (Article 89, para 3);
- Obligates the state to secure temporary housing, that is, to house the victim of domestic violence who had left their home and who has no means to independently solve their housing needs (Article 103; para 4).

This Act defines an adequate apartment in Article 90, and it lists the following criteria pertaining to:

- Special specifications in relation to how large the apartment is (in accordance to number of people expected to live in it)
- Whether the apartment is equipped with basic installations (water, electric, sanitary)
- Whether the apartment has been constructed well and is safe (the apartment must not present a life and health hazard, that is, it must not be derelict and its essential constructive elements must not be questionable, and they must have been made in accordance to laws that regulate construction)

- Protection from outside elements and provision of basic hygienic conditions (the apartment is protected from freezing weather, rain, wind and other adverse weather conditions; it also has natural light and is protected from condensation).
- If the social housing beneficiary is a person with disability, the apartment must be accessible (in relation to the degree and type of disability).

The Spatial Planning Act of the Republic of Serbia from 2010 to 2020, in Chapter 2.1. (Social Coherence) points out the multi-decade lack of state policies and action in relation to social housing, and the necessity of developing social housing in accordance to rural and urban policies on a local level, and with regard to promoting social inclusion and cohesion.

Domestic Violence Prevention Act — this law does not address issues pertaining to housing, but the issue of long-term housing for victims of domestic violence (as part of social housing policy) would be complementary to other types of victim support (as regulated by Article 31 of said Act) which aim at providing the woman who survived violence with support for recovery, empowerment and independence.

Gender Equality Act — the recently adopted law on gender equality points out that special measures and programs intended for victims of violence in the aim of violence prevention, are not to be considered discrimination. These measures and programs aim at securing a life free of violence, and include social housing (as defined by Article 52, para 3).

The Social Housing National Strategy, which is still in force³, is aimed at developing social housing for people who cannot independently afford housing in accordance with market prices. This strategy uses the European typology of homelessness and housing exclusion (ETHOS)⁴ based on three aspects defining “home”: 1) physical — it’s a physical living space, 2) social — privacy protection, 3) legal — a legal right to a home. Lack of any of these types of aspects leads to some type of homelessness which is conceptually divided into 4 groups: without a roof over ones head, without a home, insecure and inadequate housing. These four groups are further subdivided into 13 categories, one of which explicitly acknowledges women who are living in safe houses and shelters (category 4) and that they are at risk of homelessness seeing as they are provided only with temporary housing; aside from that, people facing violence are also mentioned in category 10 which pertains to insecure housing, that is, to life under threat of violence. Additionally, the strategy notes that this typology is useful for adapting residential buildings, mapping homelessness, and developing housing support systems; that all types of homelessness and housing insecurity in Serbia have been listed, and that the strategy should be implemented as set out. Unfortunately, some estimates suggested that only one tenth of the necessary funds have been approved, and there is no data pertaining to social housing for women who have survived violence or victims of violence in general.

3 This Strategy is connected to the previous Social Housing Act (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, number 72/09) which ceased to be in force when the Housing and Building Maintenance Act began being applied (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, no. 104/2016 and 9/2020 — state law).

4 The European typology of homelessness and housing exclusion — ETHOS, was developed by the European union of organizations working with the homeless (FEANTSA).

Sustainable Urban Development in Serbia Strategy to 2030: 47/2019-4 — in Chapter 4 (which analyzes the state of urban development in regards to variety and accessibility of housing — 4.1.4.2.) it is concluded that many households are potential beneficiaries of housing support services, but that determining the exact range is impossible due to the lack of a comprehensive overview of said households' finances, as well as specific housing needs of socially vulnerable categories. Moreover, it notes that a new national housing strategy is currently being developed and that it should replace the existing Social Housing Strategy and establish more possibilities for solving housing needs in accordance to the financial means of different population categories.

Roma Social Inclusion Strategy in Serbia from 2016 to 2025 — a large part of this strategy is aimed at social integration and elimination of housing poverty of the Roma population. The strategy acknowledges the disordered state of social housing and lack of social housing which is evident in the meager number of housing projects that have been completed and meager number of projects intended for housing Roma people who live in inadequate and unsafe dwellings; ad hoc housing of Roma people who had been evicted from informal neighborhoods; it notes concern over the low number of Roma families who have benefited from social housing, as well as the difficulty they face in paying monthly bills and are therefore perpetually faced with threats of eviction. It's also noted that the UN Committee for Economic, Social and Cultural Rights asked the Republic of Serbia in 2014 to broaden social housing capacities to people with low income, and to implement measures which would ensure that Roma people have access to adequate housing by improving conditions in existing neighborhoods they live in, and building new residential social housing units.

The National Housing Strategy draft from 2020 to 2030 recognizes that there are currently no permanent sustainable measures for housing domestic violence victims, that one of the reasons there is a lack of development in services provided to victims of violence is that local self-governments lack adequate information about it, and also that there is no data and research documenting the connection between domestic violence and women's housing insecurity which may lead to homelessness. It is also noted that there is no research about women and the exercise of social rights. Some of the measures this strategy foresees are public property apartment construction intended to be rented at not-for-profit prices; apartment construction intended for sale at not-for-profit prices; subventions for rent — housing aid⁵ for people defined in Article 89 of the Housing and Building Maintenance Act (among others, domestic violence victims).

5 Source: [Nacrt Nacionalne stambene strategije 2020-2030. godine](#) (in Serbian) — National Housing Strategy draft 2020-2030, Ministry of Construction, Transportation and Infrastructure, pg. 62

4. LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF SOCIAL HOUSING POLICY IN THE CITY OF BELGRADE (FOR THE TARGET GROUP OF WOMEN WHO HAVE SURVIVED VIOLENCE)

Research conducted on rehabilitation and reintegration of women who have survived violence (Lacmanovic, 2020) which encompassed 118 local self-government units, showed that Belgrade is one of 6⁶ local self-government units which (as part of the *Decisions on social protection rights and services*) regulates “protected social housing” for domestic violence victims as one form of support for independent living. Better defined conditions, measures, criteria, and an exact procedure for accessing this service are under the jurisdiction of the city government’s bodies for social services. This social protection measure can be seen as one of the measures of social housing policy (some local self-government units may, however, classify it under “innovative services”), but also represents a means of short-term and urgent provision of shelter (aside from safe houses and shelters) rather than a long-term and systemic solution to housing insecurity of women who have survived violence.

Pertaining to social housing policy, in the last 18 years (that is, since domestic violence was made a criminal act⁷) there have been 3 major decisions on how apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade are to be managed. These decisions regulate selling and renting said apartments at not-for-profit conditions (social housing) to predefined target groups. Those three decisions are:

- *Decision on terms and conditions, and manner of managing apartments constructed under the 1 100 Apartments in Belgrade project* (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 20/2003, 9/2004, 11/2005, 4/2007, 29/2007, 6/2010, 16/2010, 37/2010, 17/2012, and 8/2013)
- *Decision on terms and conditions of selling 2000 social not-for-profit apartments in Belgrade* (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 7/2005 and 25/2005)
- *Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade* (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 20/2015, 37/2016, and 114/2016)

6 This research shows that the aforementioned service exists in 65 (out of 118 local self-government units encompassed in the research), while in 6 victims have been explicitly named as a distinct target group: as persons who suffered domestic violence (Belgrade, Uzice, Pozarevac); as persons who are victims of sexual-family violence (Prijepolje, Smederevo); as victims of domestic violence (Trgoviste).

7 The criminal offence of domestic violence was adopted in 2002 in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Serbia, and then later in the Family Act of 2005.

Within these decisions it is possible to identify several social housing measures aimed at solving housing issues for various categories of people, such as:

- sale of apartments at not-for-profit prices
- rent of apartments at not-for-profit prices
- subventions for rent (housing aid)
- protected social housing

Sale of apartments at not-for-profit prices — this measure is intended for target groups defined by the first and second Decision, and entails the sale of apartments which will be paid with bank loans, while the loan itself requires a 20% down payment and will be paid off within 20 years. It is intended for people who don't have their own apartment, are employed, able to get a loan, have been residents of Belgrade for at least a year prior to the call for applications, and who qualify and rank high on the list. The last decision changes the length of residency from one to three years, and specifies that only citizens of the Republic of Serbia qualify.

Rent of apartments at not-for-profit prices — this measure is intended for target groups defined by the first and third Decision and entails renting apartments, for a predetermined period, to vulnerable groups (if they don't have their own property) who are citizens of the Republic of Serbia and have been residents of the city for at least two or three years (depending on the decision) prior to the call for applications. These people's vulnerability status is determined by the fact that their family income does not exceed 80% of the last known average salary per employee in Belgrade (before taxes).

Subventions for rent (housing aid) — this measure is set out in Article 44 of the last Decision and entails that the person renting out the social housing apartment for not-for-profit prices gets subventions on rent for a year in case the total rent (after taxes) exceeds 30% of average family monthly earnings, in a manner determined by law and other social protection regulations. The largest subvention amount (housing aid) may vary between 30% of the family's monthly earnings from para 1 of this Article, up to the amount to be paid for rent (after taxes) for the apartment in questions. This calculation is also dependent on the amount allocated in the budget for this purpose.

Protected social housing — protected social housing is intended as one of the measures aimed at vulnerable people and their families, refugees and internally displaced people who are in financial need or in collective housing, and who do not own their own property, and are interested for this type of housing. **When applying for this type of support a person may get additional points if the person is a victim of violence.** The procedure for selecting a protected social housing beneficiary is conducted by a commission formed by the Mayor of Belgrade, and consists of (among others) representatives of the city's social welfare centers. In the following section we'll review and compare protected social housing and renting apartments at not-for-profit prices (social housing) as determined by the last (and still in force) Decision which foresees such social housing policies.

Table 1 — Overview of social housing policies in the city of Belgrade’s Decisions

	Decision on terms and conditions, and manner of managing apartments constructed under the 1100 Apartments in Belgrade project	Decision on terms and conditions of selling 2000 social housing apartments at not-for-profit prices in Belgrade	Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade
Sale of apartments at not-for-profit prices	YES	YES	YES
Rent of apartments at not-for-profit prices	YES	NO	YES
Rent subventions (housing aid)	NO	NO	YES
Protected social housing	NO	NO	YES

Table 2 — Sale of apartments at not-for-profit prices and categories of people it is intended for

	Decision on terms and conditions, and manner of managing apartments constructed under the 1100 Apartments in Belgrade project	Decision on terms and conditions of selling 2000 social housing apartments at not-for-profit prices in Belgrade	Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade
Those employed in state-owned companies in the housing-utilities sector	YES	YES	NO
Those employed in state-owned companies and institutions	YES	YES	NO
Those employed in the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Serbia (Secretariat and regional city municipalities)	YES	YES	NO
Those employed in medical institutions	YES	YES ⁸	NO
Those employed at the Belgrade University and other scientific institutions	YES	YES	NO
Those employed in elementary and high schools	YES	YES ⁹	NO

8 Within this category (and only as part of this Decision) persons employed in social welfare institutions have also been included.

9 Within this category (and only as part of this Decision) persons employed in state sponsored boarding schools (high school and universities) have been included.

Those employed at judicial institutions: courts, prosecution	YES	YES	NO
Those employed in City Administrative Services and administration services of the city's municipalities ¹⁰	YES	YES	YES
Young married couples	YES	YES	YES
Military/war veterans with disability/members of families of those fallen in combat	YES	YES	YES
Civilians who became disabled in war	NO	NO	YES
Parents of people with disabilities	YES	YES	YES
Foster parent of a person with disability	NO	YES	YES
Person who adopted a person with disability	NO	YES	NO
People with disability	YES	YES	YES
Independent artists	YES	YES	YES
Worthy athletes	YES	YES	YES
People who have tenancy rights/ are renting apartments (with no time limit on the lease) which are owned by regular citizens	NO	NO	YES
People who have tenancy rights/ are renting apartments (with no time limit on the lease) owned by endowment trusts	NO	NO	YES
People moving out of unhygienic buildings and apartments and derelict buildings	NO	NO	YES
People who have been granted the right to financial assistance in accordance to social welfare provisions, and who are deemed incapable of work and have no family members currently employed	NO	NO	YES
Refugees and internally displaced people	NO	NO	YES

¹⁰ Without the possibility of participation of those elected, named and placed in those positions.

Table 3 — Rent of apartments at not-for-profit prices by categories of target groups

<p>Decision on terms and conditions, and manner of managing apartments constructed under the 1100 apartments in Belgrade project (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 20/2003, 9/2004, 11/2005, 4/2007, 29/2007, 6/2010, 16/2010, 37/2010, 17/2012, and 8/2013)</p>	<p>Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 20/215, 37/2016, and 114/2016)</p>
<p>This decision does not contain a list of special categories, rather renting out of apartments at not-for-profit prices is aimed at people who have been defined as being vulnerable (people without adequate housing). According to the conditions/criteria for accessing this right we may conclude that the following categories are encompassed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. people who have gained the right to financial aid 2. people whose total family earnings do not exceed 80% of the last known average monthly income in Belgrade (without tax) 3. single parents 4. foster parents who live with the child in one household 5. parents of children with mental disability who are not in social institutions 6. people with disabilities 7. self-reliant beneficiaries of monthly payments who enjoy said rights based on the fact that they are family members of victims of war (in accordance to state provisions) 8. people who are have access to a room or bed in a shelter 9. people living in rooms in a temporary shelter which cannot be considered an apartment because they do not provide the bare necessities as housing, that is, there is no electricity, water or sanitation (shack, attic or basement rooms, storage, etc.) 10. people renting out apartments 11. people who have tenancy rights, that is, they are renting an apartment without a time limit on the contract or there may be a time limit specified, while the apartment is owned by a regular citizen who may or may not live there as well 12. people living in communal rooms in a residential building 13. people who are illegally living in someone else’s apartment or an illegally constructed building 	<p>This decision defines a range of people for whom these social housing measures are intended (in general), and the specific measure of renting apartments at not-for-profit prices. The range of people is as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. veterans and people with disabilities from wars, and family members of those fallen in the wars after August 17th 1990, in accordance with provisions pertaining to protections for veterans/people with disabilities and City of Belgrade provisions; 2. people who have tenancy rights/have rented out an apartment with no time limit on the lease, while those apartments are owned by regular citizens, and in the aim of returning those apartments to the owners 3. people who have tenancy rights/have rented out an apartment with no time limit on the lease, while the apartments are owned by endowment trusts; 4. people who are moving out of unhygienic buildings and apartments that may become derelict; 5. people who have are financial aid beneficiaries in accordance to provisions pertaining to social security and ensuring citizens’ social security, and who are unemployed and have no family members currently employed 6. those employed in the City Administration service and administrative services of other city’s municipalities, and those employed in institutions and state owned companies which were founded by the city of Belgrade; 7. refugees and internally displaced people; 8. young married couples; 9. parents or guardians of people with psychological or physical disabilities, mental disability or who are developmentally challenged; 10. people with disability; 11. independent artists; 12. worthy athletes and athletes competing on an international level

Women who have survived violence or domestic violence since the moment that act legally became a crime — as was the case with the Criminal Code’s regulation of domestic violence — that is, in the past 18 years, are mentioned as a distinct target group in only the last Decision of the city of Belgrade (out of 3 in total), and only in relation to protected social housing¹¹. Other measures aimed at solving housing issues — sale and rent of apartments at not-for-profit prices and rent subventions, do not encompass women who have survived violence or victims of domestic violence as part of the 22 categories of existing target group.

4.1. Exercising social housing policy rights in practice on the territory of the City of Belgrade

In order to determine what exercising the right to social housing was like in the past and is like now in relation to women who have survived violence (in the last 18 years¹²), we filed a request for information of public importance and sent it to relevant institutions:

1. The Mayor’s Cabinet, that is, to services who are responsible for implementing these decisions: Secretariat for Social Services of the City Administration service of the city of Belgrade, and the Secretariat for Property and Legal Matters of the Administration Service of the city of Belgrade.
2. The City’s Center for Social Welfare

The questions we sent to **the Mayor’s Cabinet (the Secretariat for Property and Legal Matters of the Administration Service of the city of Belgrade)** focused on:

- The number and date of calls for applications for social housing purchases. The properties in question are either considered public property under ownership of the city of Belgrade, or the city of Belgrade has special ownership rights
- Whether victims of violence had been categorized as one of the priority target groups for getting access to the right to solve their housing issues, on the aforementioned call for applications (how many calls and which years)
- If victims had been categorized as one of the priority groups, how many of them had filed applications, and how many were selected to be beneficiaries (separate for each call for applications)
- Finances available, that is, secured for purchasing and renting social housing on the aforementioned calls (separate for each call for applications)
- Number of calls for applications for protected social housing; number of people who applied on the basis of being a domestic violence victim, and the number of people who

11 Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 20/215, 37/2016, and 114/2016)

12 That is, since the moment domestic violence was made a criminal act: Criminal Code (2002); Family Law (2005)

were selected to be beneficiaries on the basis of the last (still in force) Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade¹³

ANSWER FROM THE SECRETARIAT FOR PROPERTY AND LEGAL MATTERS
OF THE CITY ADMINISTRATIVE SERVICE OF THE CITY OF BELGRADE

The city Secretariat for Property and Legal Matters of the Administrative Service of the city of Belgrade answered our request for information in the following manner:

The number and dates of calls for applications for purchasing and renting social housing apartments owned by the city of Belgrade or over which the city of Belgrade has special ownership rights: from 2002 to 2020, there were 4 calls for sale of apartments at not-for-profit prices, as well as 7 calls for providing apartments for rent to vulnerable people and people who do not have housing, and who are not able to pay market prices for housing. Also, as part of the “Let’s Build a Home Together” — UNOPS, we had 5 public calls for applications for protected social housing.

Were victims of violence categorized as one of the priority target groups in relation to solving their housing issues in these calls (how many calls and which years)? Victims of violence were not among the priority groups in any of the calls.

Finances, that is, securing resources for purchasing and renting social housing in these calls (separately for each call): **Calls made by the city of Belgrade for solving housing needs of vulnerable groups are financed from the city of Belgrade’s budget. Other calls are accomplished through donations while the city of Belgrade gives 30% of the total funds needed for construction.**

Number of calls for protected social housing; number of people who applied for this on the basis of being victims of domestic violence, and number of people who were selected as beneficiaries on the basis of the last (and still in force) Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade: **Since the Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade (amended in 2016) there have been no calls for protected social housing.**

ANSWER OF THE CITY’S CENTER FOR SOCIAL WELFARE

Questions sent to the **City’s Center for Social Welfare** (in accordance to the Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade¹⁴) focused on:

- Their involvement into the work of the Commission which conducts the selection procedure for choosing a beneficiary for protected social housing

13 (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 20/215, 37/2016, and 114/2016)

14 Article 47 (“Official Gazette of the City of Belgrade”, no. 20/215, 37/2016, and 114/2016)

- Number of candidates who applied and who were acknowledged as being victims of violence, and number of these candidates who were selected as beneficiaries based on this right
- Manner in which victims of violence were granted protected social housing before 2015

The City Center for Social Welfare answered our inquiry by stating that employees of the City's Center for Social Welfare had been involved in selection procedures of protected social housing beneficiaries. In relation to other questions they told us that they don't have the information and directed us to the Secretariat for Social Protection of the City's Administration Service of the city of Belgrade, and the Sector for Refugees, Internally Displaced People and Migrations.

5. SOCIAL HOUSING POLICY MODELS (PERTAINING TO WOMEN WHO HAVE SURVIVED VIOLENCE) — EXAMPLES FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION

Seeing as housing directly influences a woman's decision to leave the abuser, comprehensive protection and support policies for women surviving violence should encompass social housing measures, while financially vulnerable women, unemployed women, single mothers, members of several marginalized groups should be given special attention. Keeping this in mind, let's review examples from Europe.

Post World War II Europe was confronted with ruin, impoverished populace and skyrocketing homelessness which all necessitated a state run approach to massive housing construction. Slowly, focus shifted from mass residential construction to special target groups, and with the rise in importance of ecological issues, urban and sustainable development also began to factor in. Seeing as different European nations were facing different problems, the European Union left it to every state to develop its own social housing policies in relation to the specific problems it had to address. In some countries, such as Great Britain, social housing was mostly provided by renting out state owned apartments, while in the Netherlands and Germany social housing also entailed financial assistance for rent regardless of whether the apartments in question are state owned or private property (PALGO Center, 2010: 65). What all countries have in common are limited budgets, so they all try to allocate resources where they are most needed depending on their finances and resources.

The EU policy of free movement of people and goods influenced the development of social housing policy through: regionalization (localization) — where jurisdiction and finance were lowered from the state level to the level of local self-governments, as well as liberalization as can be seen in the inclusion of the non-profit and private capital sectors in social housing. Due to these factors we have three modalities and concepts of social housing: 1) Residual — this model is minimal and short-term, and only available when other modalities are unavailable and it is exclusively aimed at the most vulnerable households; 2) General — available to all households with limited resources and 3) Universal — which aims at offering apartments to the general populace (PALGO Center, 2010: 68).

Specific housing budgets of EU countries vary and correlate to distinct needs, and ownership is also regulated in different ways: in some places it's a part of the public sector, in others it's a partnership between the state and the private sector, and in some other examples the non-profit sector is also included.

Finance and organizational modalities also vary depending on the number, practical circumstances, breadth of the problem, and scope of target groups, degree of localization and deregulation, and who is responsible for accomplishing the work (PALGO Center, 2010: 72). A conclusion which may be reached through comparative analysis of social housing policies in various countries is that they differ but all, to a greater or lesser extent, are available under specific conditions to and aimed at particular target groups. Therefore, in the following section we will focus on models which are aimed at the target group of women victims of violence.

Availability of housing to women and their children following their stay in a safe-house is something that directly influences how long they will stay in these safe-houses. In the *Report on specialized services for women in Europe by the European Network of Women against Violence*, in which they analyzed the situation in 46 countries, in 12 countries women and their children could not find housing at accessible prices upon leaving safe-houses, 22 countries don't have a public housing plan, while there are public housing plans in 9 countries (WAVE, 2015: 33). Seeing as women have difficulties finding housing, **in relation to granting social housing**, Austria, the Netherlands and Belgium **give higher priority to women in safe-houses**. Therefore, women and their children in situations where they must leave safe-houses are made a social housing priority group, and they are offered solutions to permanently solve their housing issues and at affordable prices, too — so as to prevent them from returning to the abuser and living with him.

Even though it isn't a permanent solution to housing issues, half-way houses give women who are leaving safe-houses some time to reintegrate. A total of 15 countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Malta, the Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland and Great Britain) reported that some safe-houses may offer this service to some women (WAVE, 2015: 34). Denmark has began a pilot project which deals with this problem, Italy has reported that some safe-houses refer women to half-way houses where the rent is kept very low for a year. Spain makes it possible for women and their children who are leaving safe-houses to find housing under mentorship, lasting up to 18 months. Lithuania, and partially Portugal, provide social housing to women who are leaving safe-houses which they used as temporary housing (WAVE, 2015: 34).

In Slovenia, **women who are surviving violence get additional points on municipal calls for applications for not-for-profit apartments** if in the last three years they had spent time in a safe-house, crisis center or if centers for social welfare are aware of the violence they have suffered.

Aside from being given an advantage as a priority group for social housing, Great Britain offers several measures depending on whether the victim will stay in accommodations she has lived in up till then or if she'll go to another location. Alongside the measures in various countries already mentioned, special attention is given in situations where the victim intends to stay in the apartment from which the abuser has been removed, or which he has vacated. In these situations, after the value of the apartment has been ascertained, as have the needs and circumstances of the people involved, local government bodies are encouraged to provide adequate measures to ensure that the woman and her children are kept safe. Aforementioned measures are: securing doors and

windows, putting in additional locks, fire-resistant mail boxes, smoke alarms and fire-extinguishing equipment, alarms, intercom systems, video surveillance, and “panic rooms” — where the victim may hide and call the police (United Kingdom Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2018).

In the aim of preventing violence against women and femicide, in 2019 France amended its law and introduced numerous measures, among others is a measure aimed at solving housing problems for victims of violence. These changes introduced a new rule that, if requested, the victim may stay in the original house/apartment regardless of ownership. If the victims chooses to leave the home, she may get access to **financial aid in order to solve her housing issues** (pay a deposit, guarantee intent to rent, or for first month’s rent). Aside from that, victims of violence may be granted emergency housing from the state’s housing stock (LOI no. 2019-1480 du 28 décembre 2019 visant à agir contre les violences au sein de la famille (1)).

5.1. Half-way house for women victims of violence, Skoplje, North Macedonia

The half-way house and assisted living house is intended for women in a dire financial situation and who have left a violent partner or family member. These women have no housing otherwise, and are not earning money (or are earning inadequate sums to rent). This model of reintegration services intended for women who have survived violence and their children entails free, temporary housing for up to 24 months. It was established in Skoplje, North Macedonia, in 2020, and is the only one of its kind in the whole region.

The house is located in the city center, has 4 bedrooms, 2 baths, and communal rooms such as: living room, kitchen, balcony, yard. It’s near a kindergarten, elementary and high schools, a hospital, a supermarket, a pharmacy. It’s connected to all parts of Skoplje by bus lines. This model is effective in ceasing isolation of victims of violence (separating them from people who may help, support services, institutions they may turn to for protection), and allows women and children to reintegrate into the community.

A women who uses this half-way house gets one bedroom with beds for her and her children, while she shares the other rooms with the other women residing there. The city of Skoplje pays the living expenses for the house (food, personal hygiene for women and children (babies as well), and cleaning products), and monthly expenses and salaries for the women offering support at the half-way house. House management has been handed to the National Network against Violence against Women and Domestic Violence, which initiated this service and established cooperation with the city of Skoplje in order to ensure its survival. When needed and in accordance to possibilities, the Network provides additional resources for the house through projects supported by international funders.

The team of representatives from a women’s non-governmental organization who run the house are: a social worker who also conducts managerial work for the house, a lawyer, a psychologist, and a career and improvement consultant. The team provides support on a daily basis depending on the women’s needs. Upon moving into the house the team develops an individual plan harmonized with the woman’s needs and her children’s needs.

Admission and services at the Half-Way House:

Evaluation of the risk of violence repetition, and security risks to women and children.

If there is still a medium or high risk of violence against the woman and children, the woman will first be directed to support services provided by the NGO sector (SOS line, safe-house), as well as violence prevention services offered by institutions. These situations require that violence ceases first, and only then may the woman be involved into reintegration programs in the half-way house.

Women's security and safety. The house rules were established so as to maintain quality of life in the community (there are always several families at the house), as well as to provide security and safety to all women residing at the house and its staff. Upon admission to the house, the woman is informed about the house rules and she must sign a written statement accepting said rules.

Individual plan development. If there is no risk to the woman's and her children's safety, in cooperation with the woman the team will map her social, financial, educational, health and legal needs (in accordance to the already developed questionnaires for each of these issues) and develop an individual plan of services which entails a time frame for each activity.

Service provision. While living in the half-way house the team will provide psycho-social and health related services to the woman and her children in order to empower her independence, and they will direct her to programs for improving her qualifications, connect her to employers in order to get a job, provide legal services and means of support and help.

5.2. Comprehensive model of social housing accessible to all: Vienna, Austria

One of the most successful and best known examples of successful social housing models is the Viennese model which has been developing and has been perfected for more than twenty years, and its dedication to social cohesion and equality have been improving it continually. Data shows that 45% of Vienna's housing stock is allocated to social housing (stock is rented out for social housing with no time limit), while 60% of the populace receives subventions for apartments or lives in housing owned by municipalities. Every year, 7030 social housing apartments are built on average (Housing in Vienna, Annual Report 2018/2019). In 2018, the city of Vienna organized nine calls for applications for a total of eleven housing projects, and aside from requiring that the new apartments must be of high quality and accessible (in relation to finance, architecture, social sustainability, and ecology), the apartments also had to fulfil other standards, such as that they must be built to suit the needs of single parents and must offer access to communal content which must be easily accessible (kindergartens, schools, stores, cultural institutions, retirement homes, playgrounds, parks). The innovative point of constructing apartments suited to the needs of single parents introduces the concept of having the organizational structure satisfies housing needs but it also must make everyday communication and interaction easier, as well as assure privacy and independence of single parents and their children (Housing in Vienna, Annual Report 2018/2019: 20).

An innovation that has received a lot of international attention is the "subvention housing zone" as a construction category. This idea is based on the fact that just as the state is responsible for financing educational and medical institutions, or construction of transportation infrastructure,

so it should also be responsible for creating the conditions necessary for affordable housing that will be accessible to everyone in society. The portion of (apartments) receiving subventions as part of this zoning category is on average 2/3 of all housing area of the residential building being constructed. This manner of construction also makes it possible to have affordable housing all over the city, and enables people of various social statuses to live in the same area, in all municipalities in Vienna.

Establishing and maintaining social cohesion is a special aspect of Vienna's social housing program. Because of it, there are special expert teams which are in charge of networking and coordinating in the aim of establishing neighborly relations and solving potential conflicts. These teams, therefore, establish contact with residents, shop owners, and decision makers in order to develop communication and establish networks, provide support, help and inform the neighborhood when needed. Aside from periodically keeping the neighborhood informed, residents of social housing zones are encouraged to actively participate and give — for examples, going on guided tours of the neighborhood (on foot or by bike), go to exhibits, historical overviews of the neighborhood, group excursions to other urban areas, attend theater plays after which citizens can ask questions or share their opinions about communal living. Some of the projects realized as part of establishing neighborly relations are “Learning Tutor” which provided an opportunity for intergenerational connections; “Welcome Neighbor” which gave longtime residents an opportunity to provide support to those moving into the neighborhood; and “Municipal Residential Choir” which serves to allow people to meet each other or strengthen their connections.

In case some households are facing financial problems they have the right to get monthly financial aid which helps them keep their apartment (should they get sick or lose their jobs). Aside from that, this model offers a great degree of security because lease contracts are made without any time limits attached, residents participate in running the building, and they have the right to renovate their apartment without the landlord's prior approval (PALGO Center, 2010: 97-98).

The Viennese safe-house for women surviving violence and their children assists women in finding a new home after leaving the safe-house, in case they are not able to go back to their original home. In case it's needed, consultants direct women to accommodations for mothers and children, or homes for very young or single mothers, that is, to the city of Vienna Housing Service. Should there be a risk of the woman losing her family's home while at the safe-house because her abusive partner who still lives there refuses to pay rent and the bills, the safe-house consultants will contact the apartment owner to inform him/her that the woman fully intends on continuing to live there upon leaving the safe-house (Ignjatovic, Pesic, 2012: 96).

Half-way house living: from 2006 the Viennese safe-house provides this type of housing in houses and apartments to women who no longer have a need for the safe-house's intense support service but who cannot turn to other organizations for accommodation or do not have the right to get emergency housing provided by the city. In this way the woman's housing needs can be taken care of, and they can also periodically get support from social services so as to regain their independence (Ignjatovic, Pesic, 2012: 96).

6. CONCLUSION

Based on everything we've reviewed thus far, we may conclude the social housing policies in Serbia are partial, sporadic and erratic, and that their development, creation and realization — in a “modern” interpretation of those terms — are just beginning. When considering social cohesion, it's concerning that 7.3% of Serbia's population lives in absolute poverty, that half a million people are not able to satisfy basic needs, and that more than one third are at risk of poverty or social exclusion. Despite all of this, housing poverty has not been adequately addressed and systemically included into social protection policy, that is, aside from taking into consideration existential needs the criteria for determining the level of risk of poverty does not really consider housing needs. In Serbia, the proportion of social housing in the total housing stock is less than one percent (0.78% — National Housing Strategy draft 2020-2030) while in some European nations that number climbs up to 35 % (OECD Affordable Housing Database; OECD — Social Policy Division — Directorate of Employment, Labor and Social Affairs, 2020). All of this leads to the conclusion that the state must take on a more active role in creating and implementing social housing policies.

Research shows that the most numerous group of homeless people in Serbia are women over the age of 65. It's important to note that aside from the risk of becoming victims of violence, women in a disadvantageous financial-housing situation are also faced with the risk of homelessness in case they decide to leave their violent partner or family member. Violent partners have been identified as one of the most common reasons leading to female homelessness. In some countries the rate of homeless women who have survived violence goes up to 100% (Spain) and 93% (Sweden), while among regional countries that rate goes up to 50% (Hungary).

Analysis of housing insecurity among women who have survived violence (among those who had turned to the Autonomous Women's Center during the preceding five years) shows that a bit more than one fourth (27%) has complete or partial ownership of the home they live in, while two thirds (63%) live in a home that belongs to someone else (their parents or their friends, temporary accommodation of some sort, her partner's or his parent's apartment).

Also, more than half of the women who turned to the Autonomous Women's Center for legal aid noted that at the time they were the sole and direct provider for their children. Financial and housing instability are the most significant and well documented problems faced by single parent families, among which, single mother families are most common. A distinct aspect of financial deprivation is housing deprivation and it frequently results in moving houses after a divorce — usually to one of worse quality and in a worse neighborhood. All of this points to the fact that there is a real need to create and implement preventive measures and measures aimed at solving the housing needs of women (who are surviving violence) and their children.

The Republic of Serbia's legal framework recognizes people who have survived domestic violence as a category which should be a target group of social housing policies. In that regard, the Housing and Building Maintenance Act is of great importance, seeing as it explicitly names “victims of domestic violence”, and prescribes the following measures:

- Eviction and relocation procedures must always be done in accordance to the principle of protecting especially vulnerable people
- Housing support for domestic violence victims who are without an apartment or adequate apartment, and don't have adequate means to independently pay market prices and solve their housing needs
- Emergency housing provision for domestic violence victims (temporary accommodation).

The legal framework of the city of Belgrade in relation to social housing in the last 18 years (2002-2020) is defined by three major Decisions that regulate management of apartments owned by the city of Belgrade. Since domestic violence was made a criminal act (that is, in the past 18 years), women who have survived violence, or domestic violence victims, have been acknowledged only in relation to protected social housing (which is an emergency type of housing provision and temporary), but their housing needs have not been addressed in a more long-term and sustainable way.

When it comes to exercising the right to social housing for women who have survived violence on the territory of the city of Belgrade, there have been a total of 16 calls for applications in the last 18 years (4 for sale of apartments at not-for-profit prices, 7 for rent of apartments to vulnerable people and people without housing who are not able to pay market prices to provide housing to themselves, and 5 public calls for applications for protected social housing). Victims of violence were not designated a priority status in any of the calls for applications. Since the adoption of the Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade (amended in 2016) not one call for applications for protected social housing has been made.

It's commendable that legislators saw it fitting to include victims of domestic violence in Article 89 of the Housing and Building Maintenance Act as one category of beneficiaries which housing support is aimed at. However, aside from the existing practice of placing domestic violence victims in safe-houses, which are a necessary but temporary solution, Serbia still does not have permanent and sustainable measures aimed at securing housing for domestic violence victims (National Housing Strategy draft 2020-2030). The GREVIO expert report points out that even though the National Social Housing Strategy establishes a blueprint for social housing and specific employment services for women victims of domestic violence, it also notes that these programs are not a significant improvement because only a very small number of municipalities can practically offer them to women. Considering all of these facts, it is evident that women who have survived violence must be included as a distinct category of social housing beneficiaries. Also, policy measures aimed at long-term and sustainable solutions of housing needs of women who have survived violence must be created and implemented.

When we take into consideration the needs of women who have survived violence and who had turned to the Autonomous Women's Center, and if we take into consideration the Housing and Building Maintenance Act, provisions of the Istanbul Convention which address housing provision for women who have survived violence, it becomes evident that the following should be done:

- Local decisions pertaining to conditions and manner of managing and selling apartments must include the target group of women who have survived violence as one of the priority groups.
- Build new residential housing or allocate existing ones (belonging to local self-governments) to half-way housing for women who have survived violence.
- Following the example of the city of Belgrade, at least a year of financial support must be provided to women who have survived violence, allowing a number of women to cover costs of living (in the intermediate period between safe-houses and permanent housing).
- Provide financial support or material support for renovation of inadequate housing.
- Make it possible for women who have survived violence to have their housing monthly bills reduced or eliminated altogether.
- If, after the abuser has been removed from it, a victim remains in a mutually owned / rented out apartment that she shares with the abuser, or an apartment that she owns (based on an eviction from a family home order, in accordance to Article 198, para 2, point 1 of the Family Law of the Republic of Serbia), and following property value assessment, as well as the assessment of circumstances and needs, local authorities can insure the safety of the victim and her children by applying adequate measures. These measures may include: installing new or securing existing doors and windows; installing additional locks; installing alarms, intercom systems, and video surveillance.

It is our firm belief that everyone deserves decent living arrangements, and in practice there are still too many people to whom this right has been denied. Keeping that in mind, it's important that the state, private sector and nonprofit sector invest effort and continuously act to ensure that everyone is taken care of in this regard, and especially women and children surviving violence. This represents an opportunity for us to develop a new model of social housing — one which offers a chance to establish new and diverse neighborhoods, which fit the needs and interests of the people who live there.

7. LITERATURE

Economic Commission for Europe Geneva (2006). [GUIDELINES ON SOCIAL HOUSING: Principles and Examples](#). UNITED NATIONS, New York and Geneva.

European Federation of National Organizations Working with the Homeless. *Women experiencing violence and homelessness: interlinked and unaddressed gender specific needs*, Brussels, Belgium. Available at: https://www.feantsa.org/public/user/Resources/Position_papers/FEANTSA_background_paper_Women's_Homelessness_and_GBV.pdf (Accessed on January 12th 2021).

Ignjatovic, T., Pesic, D. (2012). *Poverty risks for women with experiences of violence*, Autonomous Women's Center, Belgrade. Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.womenngo.org.rs/images/publikacije-dp/2012/Rizici_od_siromastva_za_zene_sa_iskustvom_nasilja_-_inicijative_za_unapredjenje_politike_socijalne_inkluzije.pdf (Accessed on May 21st 2021).

Ignjatovic, T. (2020). *Social policy in Serbia — from a gender perspective and the perspective of women with experiences of gender based violence*. Autonomous Women's Center, Belgrade. Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.womenngo.org.rs/images/publikacije-dp/2020/Usluge_rehabilitacije_i_integracije_za_zene_koje_su_prezivele_nasilje_u_Republici_Srbiji.pdf (Accessed on December 28th 2020).

Ignjatovic, T. (2021). *Challenges in attaining protection and support for women with experience of violence in partner relationships, and their children, in Serbia*, Autonomous Women's Center, Belgrade.

Lacmanovic, V. (2020). *Rehabilitation and integration services for women who have survived violence in the Republic of Serbia*, Autonomous Women's Center, Belgrade, 2020. Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.womenngo.org.rs/images/publikacije-dp/2020/Usluge_rehabilitacije_i_integracije_za_zene_koje_su_prezivele_nasilje_u_Republici_Srbiji.pdf (Accessed on December 28th 2020).

Marinkovic Jelena, Nada Durickovic, and Amela Bicic (2019). *Gender based violence against Roma women, and availability of support services*. Roma Center for Women and Children — Daje, Belgrade. Available (in Serbian) at: <https://romadaje.org/rodno-zasnovano-nasilje-nad-romkinjama-i-dostupnost-usluga-podrske/> (Accessed on: January 7th 2021).

Municipal Department 50, Section for Housing Research and International Relations (2020). *Housing in Vienna*, Administrative Group for Housing, Housing Construction, Urban Renewal and Women's Issues, Town Hall, Vienna.

National Alliance for Local Economic Development (NALED) (2020). *Only one in every six rural women own real-estate*. National Alliance for Local Economic Development (NALED), Belgrade, Serbia. Available (in Serbian) at: <https://www.naled.rs/vest-nekretninu-poseduje-tek-svaka-sesta-zena-na-selu-3631> (Accessed on September 29th 2021).

OECD Affordable Housing Database; OECD — Social Policy Division — Directorate of Employment, Labour and Social Affairs (Last updated 6/11/2020). *PH4.2 social rental housing stock*. Paris, France. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/els/family/PH4-2-Social-rental-housing-stock.pdf> (Accessed on December 28th 2020).

PALGO Center (2010). *Social Housing — Overview of housing policies in Serbia and select European countries*. PALGO Center, for the publisher Dusan Damnjanovic, Kneginje Ljubice 14, Belgrade. Available (in Serbian) at: <https://dokumen.tips/documents/socijalno-stanovanje-stanovanje-prikaz-stambenih-politika-srbije-i-odabranih-zemalja.html> (Accessed on: September 17th 2021).

The Commissioner for the Protection of Equality (2015). *The Commissioner for the Protection of Equality's special report on discrimination of women*, Belgrade, Serbia. Available (in Serbian) at: http://ravnopravnost.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/images_files_Poseban%20izvestaj%20Poverenika%20za%20zastitu%20ravnopravnosti%20o%20diskriminaciji%20zena.doc

Republic of Serbia. 2018 report which follows the Commission's announcement to the European Parliament, Council, and European Economic and Social Committee, and Regional Committee — Announcement on EU Expansion Policy for 2018 — The Commission's draft document (2019).

European Commission, available (in Serbian) at: [https://www.mei.gov.rs/upload/documents/eu_dokumenta/godisnji_izvestaji_ek_o_napretku/izvestaj_ek_o_srbiji\(1\).pdf](https://www.mei.gov.rs/upload/documents/eu_dokumenta/godisnji_izvestaji_ek_o_napretku/izvestaj_ek_o_srbiji(1).pdf)

Republic of Serbia. 2019 report which follows the Commission's announcement to the European Parliament, Council, and European Economic and Social Committee, and Regional Committee — Announcement on EU Expansion Policy for 2019 — The Commission's draft document (2019).

European Commission, available (in Serbian) at: https://www.mei.gov.rs/upload/documents/eu_dokumenta/godisnji_izvestaji_ek_o_napretku/20190529-serbia-report_SR - REVIDIRANO.pdf

Expert group against violence against women and domestic violence (GREVIO) (2020). GREVIO report on the (basic) assessment procedure on legislative and other measures used to apply the Council of Europe's Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence. Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.rodnaravnopravnost.gov.rs/sites/default/files/2021-01/GREVIO_Izvestaj%20o%20bazicnom%20postupku%20procene%20stanja_Srbija.pdf (accessed on June 1st 2021).

Republic Institute for Statistics (2014), *Labor Force and Agricultural Households' Activities*, Republic of Serbia. Available (in Serbian) at: <https://pod2.stat.gov.rs/ObjavljenePublikacije/Popis2012/Radna%20snaga.pdf> (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Tomanovic, S., Ljubicic, M., Stojanovic, D., (2014). *Single parent families in Serbia — a sociological study*, "Cigoja Press", Institute for Sociological Research of the Philosophy Faculty of Belgrade, Belgrade. Available (in Serbia) at: https://isi.f.bg.ac.rs/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Smiljka-Tomanovic_Milana-Ljubicic_Dragan-Stanojevic-Jednoroditeljske_porodice_studija-libre.pdf (accessed on: December 28th 2020).

United Kingdom Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government (2018). *Improving access to social housing for victims of domestic abuse*, London, United Kingdom. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/improving-access-to-social-housing-for-victims-of-domestic-abuse/improving-access-to-social-housing-for-victims-of-domestic-abuse> (accessed on June 2nd 2021).

WAVE — Women against Violence Europe (2015). *WAVE Report 2015 — on the role of specialist women's support services in Europe*, WAVE — Women against Violence Europe, Vienna. Available at: https://wave-network.org/wp-content/uploads/WAVE_Report_2015.pdf (accessed on June 2nd 2021).

8. DOCUMENTS

The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (adopted by the Council of Europe on May 11th 2011 in Istanbul). Law on Ratifying the Council of Europe's Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia" — International Contracts, number 012/12). Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.womenngo.org.rs/images/pdf/Convention_Serbian.pdf.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

International Treaty on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (adopted at the UN General Assembly on December 16th 1966, by GA resolution 2200A (XXI). Confirmed by Law on Ratification ("Official Gazette of Socialist Federative Republic of Yugoslavia", number 7/71). Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.ombudsman.co.me/docs/Pakt_o_ekonomskim_socijalnim_i_kulturnim_pravima.doc (accessed on December 28th 2020).

National Social Housing Strategy. ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", no. 13/2012). Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.mgsi.gov.rs/sites/default/files/NACIONALNA_STRATEGIJA_SOCIJALNOG_STANOVANJA_0.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

National Gender Equality Strategy from 2016 to 2020. Available (in Serbian) at: <https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/docs/ELECTRONIC/102844/124487/F281260892/SRB102844%20Srb.pdf> (accessed on January 11th 2021).

National Housing Strategy draft 2020-2030. Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.mgsi.gov.rs/sites/default/files/Nacionalna_stambena_strategija_NACRT_1.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Decision on social protection rights and services of the city of Belgrade ("Official Gazette of the city of Belgrade", no. 55/2011, 8/2012 — changed, 8/2012, 42/2012, 65/2012, 31/2013, 57/2013, 37/2014, 82/2015, 4/2016, 37/2016, 56/2016, 114/2016, 102/2017, 50/2018, 103/2018 and 115/2019). Available (in Serbian) at: http://gcsrbg.org/pdf/odluka_o_pravima_i_uslugama_socijalne_zastite.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Decision on management of apartments belonging to the city of Belgrade ("Official Gazette of the city of Belgrade", no. 20/2015, 37/2016 and 114/2016).

Decision on conditions and manner of management of apartments built for the 1100 Apartments in Belgrade project ("Official Gazette of the city of Belgrade", no. 20/2003, 9/2004, 11/2005, 4/2007, 29/2007, 6/2010, 16/2010, 37/2010, 17/2012 and 8/2013).

Decision on selling 2000 social housing apartments at no-for-profit prices ("Official Gazette of the city of Belgrade", no. 7/2005, and 25/2005).

General Declaration on the Rights of Man (adopted and proclaimed by the General Assembly Resolution 217A(III) on December 10th 1948).

Revised European Social Charter ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia — International Treaties", no. 42/09). Available at: http://ravnopravnost.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/images_files_Revidirana_Evropska_socijalna_povelja_SE.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Sustainable Urban Development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia to 2030: 47/2019-4 ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", number 47, from June 28th 2019). Available (in Serbian) at: <http://www.pravno-informacioni-sistem.rs/SlGlasnikPortal/eli/rep/sgrs/vlada/strategija/2019/47/1/reg> (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Social Inclusion Strategies for Roma People in the Republic of Serbia from 2016 to 2025. Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.ljudskaprava.gov.rs/sites/default/files/dokument_file/strategija_za_socijalno_ukljucivanje_roma_i_romkinja_2016_2025_0.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Constitution of the Republic of Serbia ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", number 98/06) Available (in Serbian) at: http://www.parlament.gov.rs/upload/documents/Ustav_Srbije_pdf.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Public Property Act (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, no. 72/2011, 88/2013, 105/2014, 104/2016 — state law, 108/2016, 113/2017 and 95/2018). Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_javnoj_svojini.html (accessed on: December 28th 2020).

Spatial Plan of the Republic of Serbia from 2010 to 2020 Act (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, no. 88/2010). Available (in Serbian) at: <https://www.mgsi.gov.rs/sites/default/files/ZAKON%20O%20PROSTORNOM%20PLANU%20RS%20OD%202010%20DO%202020.pdf> (accessed on December 28th 2020)

Gender Equality Act (2021). Available (in Serbian) at: http://www.parlament.gov.rs/upload/archive/files/lat/pdf/predlozi_zakona/2021/741-21%20-%20Lat..pdf (accessed on January 6th 2021)

Domestic Violence Prevention Act (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, no. 94/2016) Available (in Serbian) at: https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_sprecavanju_nasilja_u_porodici.html (accessed on December 28th 2020).

Housing and Building Maintenance Act (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, 104/2016 and 9/2020 — state law. Note: when this law came into force the previous law — Social Housing Act — ceased to be in force (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, number 72/09), thereby becoming the first step in regulating social housing in the Republic of Serbia).

Domestic Violence Prevention Act of the Republic of France — LOI no. 2019-1480 du 28 décembre 2019 visant à agir contre les violences au sein de la famille (1). Available (in French) at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000039684243?r=pdAWy0Va51> (accessed on: January 6th 2021).

The United Nation’s Geneva Convention on Sustainable Housing (E/ECE/1478/Rev.1). This Convention was adopted by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe member states (UNECE). Available at: http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/hlm/documents/Publications/EN_Geneva_UN_Charter_on_Sustainable_Housing.pdf (accessed on December 28th 2020).

**SOCIAL HOUSING
POLICIES — POSSIBILITIES
FOR WOMEN WHO HAVE
SURVIVED VIOLENCE,
AND HOW THEY CAN
REALIZE THEIR RIGHTS**

